

Formulating Technical Competency for General Affairs Department

Renata Ivana Ryantandi¹

¹ Business Administration in Master of Business Administration Program, Parahyangan Catholic University, Bandung, Indonesia

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*Corresponding Author:
Renata Ivana Ryantandi,

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Human resource management in the company is one of the factors that can support the company's success. In human resource management, there are some important factors that can help each function run optimally, named competency. Competency is needed to support employees in doing their jobs within the company. Based on the research before the existence of competency, human resource management in the company is less optimal in carrying out their duties. The purpose of this study is to design competencies for the General Affairs Department by knowing the condition of the company's HR management without any competency and the suitable technical competency that the General Affairs Department must apply. This research mostly uses the Competency-Based Human Resource Management theory. This research is analyzed by using a qualitative research – case study method. Respondents' data source in this study are involving managers and general affairs staff and HR staff of the company. The data is collected by interviewing the respondents and supported by the company's documents. The result of this research is the design of eight technical competency for the Department of General Affairs. The recommendation from this research is that the company should implement this competency design and hopefully the company growth may be increasingly developed.

Keywords: COMPETENCY, COMPETENCY DICTIONARY, HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Introduction

Human resource management in an organization is used to ensure that the organization has competent human resources and supports organizational goals. It has some valuable functions, such as recruitment, selection, training, development, and employee welfare arrangement. One of the ways that can be used in running its functions, human resource management can be assisted by applying competencies to support the implementation of its functions. Competency is a characteristic in the form of knowledge, skills, traits, and mindset that must be possessed by an individual to achieve the expected performance (Dubois, et al, 2004). Competency is useful for assessing whether an individual has worked optimally and contributed as they are

expected in the company by looking at the discrepancy between the standard sets by the company and the individual's work quality. Competencies can be used as the base in implementing the competency-based human resource management practice. Competency-based human resource management has an approach by looking at the competencies needed by an individual in carrying out their duties (Dubois, et al, 2004).

Previously, many researchers conducted researches related to the competency in various companies in different industries, including the Manufacturing Industry (Janan and Gomathi, 2015; Shaheen, et al, 2016), Health Industry (Gangani, McLean, & Braden, 2006; He, et al, 2015; Liang, et al, 2018), Education Industry (Modi, Gupta, & Singh, 2015), Hospitality Industry (Otoo, 2018), Banking Industry (Profiroiu and Hurbudei, 2018), Printing Industry (Nasriyah, Arham, and Aini, 2016), Steel Industry (Pandey and Guha, 2014), and Creative Industry (Muizu and Hilmiana, 2016; Aisha, et al, 2019). In previous study, it was explained that several problems within the company could be overcome by the existence of a competency dictionary. The problems found are related to changes within the organization, the quality of human resources that were less uniformed and competent (Pandey & Guha, 2014; Janani & Gomathi, 2015; Shah & Prakash, 2017; Otoo, 2018; Liang, et al, 2019; Aisha, et al, 2019; Shaheen, et al, 2019) which could affect the performance and the company's competitive advantage, then coupled with the performance evaluation system that not effective (Shet, Patil, & Chandawarkar; 2018) that couldn't figure out why a certain individual wasn't so optimal in carrying out work, and the problems faced are also in training programs that didn't match the needs of employees (Telha, et al, 2016; Liang, et al, 2017; Buker & Straub, 2017).

Based on the previous studies that have carried out in various types of different industries, it shows that competency is used in many various companies. Competency has an important role in the company. A competency supports the business that is being run to be successful (Profiroiu and Hurbudei, 2018). When a company has employees with competencies that match to the work need criteria, it can increase the effectiveness within the company (Shet, Patil, and Chandawarkar, 2018) and find the suitable competency needs also makes the work environment more productive (Shah and Prakash, 2017). It is proven that competency has connected to the company's performance because competency has functioned to support the human resource management program in improving the company's performance (Otoo, 2018).

In this study, the research was conducted on the family business that engaged in the automotive industry. The main focus of this company is the four wheeled vehicle distributor. Since the beginning, the company never used the competency for their human resource management activities. The company has several problems related to the absence of competency, including in the recruitment process to the placement of employees in the company, not based on the required competencies but still adjusted to the criteria from the user, that sometimes made the performance of employees in doing their works less optimal. In performance assessment, employees were not being assessed based on the competency. It affected the promotion and employee development programs. Employee training and development programs that have been carried out so far, have not been adapted to the employees' needs but based on the work type. From the problems found, it is hoped that the competency planning is able to find prospective employees according to their needs and employee performance

can be maximized as they're expected by the company.

This research was conducted on company A, specifically in the General Affairs Department with the results of a draft list of technical competencies for the GA department. The General Affairs Department was chosen because there are not many studies that discuss technical competency for general affairs, especially in the automotive industry and this competency design is considered as a major change for the company so that one department is selected first to test the new policy.

Research Question

This study aims to design a list of technical competencies for the General Affairs Department, with the formulation of the problems discussed are:

1. How is the company running without any competency in supporting its human resource management activities?
2. What technical competencies should the General Affairs Department have?

Literature Review

Human resource management

Human resource management is a job analysis that is used for recruiting, briefing, training, rewarding system, as well as development and a description that describe overall job activities but do not describe the results of their work (Dubois, et al, 2004). Human resource management has a function to perform job analysis, workforce planning, recruitment, training, compensation management, performance appraisal, conduct counselling and employee discipline, and build relationships with employees (Dessler, 2017). HR management has a structured job description for employees so that employees' responsibilities are measured based on the work they have done successfully.

Competency-based human resource management

Competency-based HR management uses competency as the basis for employees to succeed in doing their jobs (Dubois, et al, 2004). Competency-based HR management sees that there are differences in individual abilities so that they need to be placed in the suitable type of work so that the performance results are being maximized. Competency-based HR management will regenerate traditional human resources to focus on the company productivity (Rothwell, 2012). Competency-based HR management can also be interpreted as the implementation of HR functions within the company supported by the existence of competency standard to be a reference in every decision making in order to maintain the employee performance to achieve the organization's goals. In competency-based HR management, competency is an important element that is applied in various ways, including position profile, recruitment and selection, assessment, training, and career development (Salvatierra, Funk, and Alarcon, 2016).

Competency

Competency in general is the ability needed to do a job in a certain position. Competency is a characteristic possessed by an individual, where these characteristics effectively support the work done by them (Spencer and Spencer, 1993). Competency is directed at generating effective performance to manage change, innovation, collaboration, and decision making (Sudirman, et al, 2019). An individual is said to be competent when they can use their abilities and knowledge to produce a quality work (Telha, et all, 2016). Competencies are grouped into technical competencies and non-technical competencies, where technical competencies are job-specific competencies and non-technical competencies are general competencies that can be applied to various types of work (Rothwell, Hohne, & King, 2000). In practice, the types of competencies can be adjusted to the needs of the organization or company to achieve organizational goals.

Research method

This research is a qualitative research with case study method. The data sources are divided into two types, namely primary data derived from interviews and assisted by observational data and secondary data derived from job analysis data from the General Affairs department and the literature list of Spencer and Spencer menu competencies. The technique of collecting the data is by conducting observations and interviews with the managers and staffs from the General Affairs Department and staff from the Human Resources Department. The data validity test used is the triangulation method, used to evaluate and minimize the bias that exists in the data obtained to achieve a valid conclusion. Then in identifying the technical competencies required by the General Affairs Department, the competency menu method is used, namely selecting competencies from a modified competency list source to meet company needs (Dubois et al., 2004), the menu competencies selected in this study are the menu competencies list from Spencer and Spencer.

The research model used is:

Figure 1: Research Model

Result and discussion

HR management before the competency dictionary exist

The current condition of human resource management in the company or prior to having competence is obtained from data from observations and interviews through the respondent's point of view. There are four functions of

human resource management which became important points from the discussion with the respondents, including the recruitment and selection process, employee placement, employee promotion, and employee development.

Currently, the company is conducting a recruitment and selection process in seven stages, starting from the search for employees to prospective employees entering the company. But the important thing in this process is that every time they proceed to do the recruitment, the HR team will ask for the desired employee criteria from the department that needs it. In this case, the company uses the user's prior knowledge and experience in determining the criteria someone needs to occupy a certain position. In practice, this can cause the search for prospective employees to be less precise because not all of the set criteria are correctly chosen so that productivity is less than optimal. There are other criteria needed to see the needs of a position, namely competency. Companies that have a competency structure can assist in determining whether prospective employees who are accepted have competencies that are in accordance with the given job (Salvatierra, Funk, and Alarcon, 2016). In this case, competency helps to complete the criteria provided by the user.

Then in the employee placement process, the company uses the same criteria as the criteria during the recruitment process, but is equipped by psychological test results. In this process, the company experienced obstacles where employees did not feel suitable in the positions, they occupy so that rolling or training was needed, or in other case employees could even resign. These obstacles can be minimized by having a position profile within the company. This position profile will show the tasks, functions, and abilities needed for a position, where the ability needs can be complemented by a list of competencies (Salvatierra, Funk, and Alarcon, 2016). This can improve the suitability of the placement of employees in certain positions.

In the employee promotion process, the company conducts an assessment based on the Key Performance Indicator target, where when an employee's performance is assessed as good by his superiors and exceeds the target, he can become a candidate for promotion. Performance assessment carried out by this company can also be carried out on a competency basis, this is done to help see the standard of competency skills possessed by employees (Salvatierra, Funk, and Alarcon, 2016). This can further increase productivity and provide information to employees on the expectations of the company (Sagunthala, 2017). The performance appraisal that has been carried out by the company so far can be equipped with a competency assessment so that it will be more accurate to assist employee career development.

The last important point from the results of the interview is the employee's development. The training programs that have been created are aimed in increasing the employee's knowledge and improving their performance. Training programs can also be personalized to the needs of employees based on their competencies for the position, this can be done by looking at the results of competency assessments carried out on employees. Competency standards can help companies determine the type of training needed by employees (Salvatierra, Funk, and Alarcon, 2016). This is expected to help the training program to be held also be adjusted to the company's goals (Sagunthala, 2017).

From the four functions of human resource management above, it can be seen that the implementation process,

problems, and obstacles experienced can be minimized and overcome by the existence of competency standards within the company so that it is hoped that these functions can run more optimally.

General affairs department technical competency

In the process of designing the technical competence of the General Affairs Department, several stages are taken, the first step is the identification that is related to the vision, mission and organizational structure of the company. It is obtained from the results of interviews with respondents. The second step is to conduct an analysis related to the duties and responsibilities of the General Affairs Department assisted by job analysis data from the company. It is done to find out the work activities being researched. The third step is to identify the required competencies by looking at the competence of the Spencer and Spencer menu. The selected technical competencies are collected and discussed with the company, in this case the respondent and the company's HR team to see if the job analysis made is in accordance with the activities carried out and whether the selected competencies are appropriate to support the work activities carried out. The fourth step of the competencies that have been selected will be final validation where to review the competencies that have been determined for the general affairs department after improvements have been made from the results of the discussion, this validation process is carried out with the General Affair Manager, General Affair staff, and the company's HR team. The fifth step is to elaborate each competency into a competency dictionary based on the Spencer and Spencer competency dictionary. The sixth step is to re-validate the competency dictionary that has been compiled. The seventh step is to level competency for each position in the general affairs department. After that, the last step is to review whether the technical competencies that have been designed are in accordance with the company's needs.

Previously, it was briefly explained that the division of tasks within the General Affairs Department, this data was obtained from interviews and company job analysis. The following is a job description for the General Affairs department:

Table 1. Job Description's General Affairs Department

No.	Main task	Job Description
1.	Manage the needs of office tools and equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Manage office storage space b. Manage pantry needs c. Doing shopping for pantry and office equipment d. Manage vendor invoices e. Manage employee catering readiness
2.	Carry out licensing of company activities, borrowing and maintaining inventory vehicles, as well as coordinating company security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Manage company activity permits b. Manage operational vehicles c. Make arrangements for the use of operational vehicles d. Doing driver assignment e. Overcome problems related to operational vehicles f. Manage inventory vehicle handover process g. Monitor company security

3.	Checking and maintaining company buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Receive and analyze incoming complaints related to building problems b. Conducting survey visits to company buildings c. Perform analysis related to contractor offers for building repairs d. Carry out routine maintenance of company buildings
4.	Checking and maintaining company building facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Checking the building facilities b. Carry out routine maintenance of building facilities c. Manage repairs to building facilities

The analysis result of duties and responsibilities in the General Affairs Department, it was found that the technical competencies for the General Affairs Department were as follows:

Table 2. General Affairs Technical Competencies

No.	Competency Code	Technical Competency
1	TC-01	Concern for order, quality, and accuracy
2	TC-02	Customer Service Orientation
3	TC-03	Information Seeking
4	TC-04	Relationship Building
5	TC-05	Directiveness
6	TC-06	Analytical Thinking
7	TC-07	Communication
8	TC-08	Negotiation

Note: TC means Technical Competency and two number behinds is number of competencies

Based on the result of the identification of competencies obtained from discussions and validation with the company, eight technical competencies were found for the General Affairs Department by looking at the list of competencies of the Spencer and Spencer menus. After this, each competency will be described in the competency dictionary and leveled. The levels used in this study are:

Table 3. Competency Levelling Description

Level	Description level
0	Lack of knowledge related to abilities or skills in certain fields, requires guidance in doing simple types of work
1	Have knowledge related to abilities or skills in certain fields, can do routine types of work
2	Can use and apply abilities or skills in doing work, both routinely and not properly without guidance or direction
3	Able to use and apply abilities or skills in doing work appropriately and be able to overcome problems that arise related to the field

This leveling is based on the results of discussions with the company, in the sense of using the knowledge and experience of the company's HR team and looking at existing literature sources, it is determined that the leveling of technical competence in the General Affairs Department starts from level 0 to 3.

The last stage of this design process is to describe the level division of each competency in each position in a competency mapping, where in this process, a discussion is carried out again with the company in determining so that it can be in accordance with the standards desired by the company. In this competency mapping, there will be the name of the competency, the position in the department, and the level of competence. After the mapping process is complete, it is important to re-validate to review the suitability of the company's needs so that the competency design that is formed can support employee performance.

Conclusion

After conducting interviews, observations, discussions, and analysis of the problems faced by the company in managing its human resources, the conclusions of the research are as follows:

1. Findings regarding the state of human resource management prior to the existence of a competency dictionary both in terms of recruitment, employee placement, promotion, and employee development have so far been carried out well, but sometimes some problems are found that make employee performance less than optimal, so competency is needed to support the management of human resources within the company which is expected to improve performance better than the current condition.
2. In the process of making a technical competency design for the General Affairs Department based on an analysis of the work carried out by employees, eight technical competencies were found with competency levels starting from level 0 to level 3.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions, the following are some recommendations that can be suggested:

1. The current condition of human resource management in the company is well organized. However, the company should be able to implement the competency design that has been made for the management of its human resources so that it is expected to increase productivity, workforce planning is more accurate, and ensure the company gets the employees that are needed.
2. In the process of implementing competency-based human resource management within the company, it is better to start with a process of direction by the company's HR team so that employees in the company can understand the benefits of having competency within the company.
3. In implementing competency-based human resource management, of course, requires competency design for all departments within the company so that companies can use the stages of making competency designs for the General Affairs department as an example for making competencies in other departments within the company.

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My name is Renata Ivana Ryantandi, I'm a student from Master of Business Administration at Parahyangan Catholic University, Indonesia. I have an interest in Human Resource study, especially in Human Resource Development. You can contact me at renaryantandi@gmail.com

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